

PRAGMATICS AND COGNITION**Manzila Nuriddinovna Habibova**

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Abstract: The study of linguopragmatic approach effectively employs pragmatic intentions as a means of representing individual picture by attracting attention, interesting the reader, exerting emotional impact, activating knowledge structures, stimulating the addressee's creativity, representing the conceptual world picture. The linguopragmatic analysis is based on lexicagrammatical and linguostylistic ones, and it appears to be their logical continuation in respect of linguopragmatic interpretation of the received data.

Keywords: conceptual world picture, discourse, linguistic personality, pragmatic intention, thesaurus.

Introduction. The modern linguistics is based on the principle of anthropocentric paradigm, which contains "human factor" in the study of language. The anthropocentric scientific paradigm puts forward the new approaches to the research of language which are implemented within a number of new disciplines, such as cognitive linguistics, linguopersonology, linguoculturology, text linguistics, linguopragmatics, communicative linguistics, etc. It is acknowledged that new perspective trends in linguistics should be investigated through anthropocentric approach. General assumptions are the following:

- the basic notion of paradigm, its historical development and classification are key figures in penetrating deep meaning of linguistic personality;
- anthropocentric paradigm in the light of interdisciplinary approach, which includes cognitive linguistics, linguopragmatics, linguoculturology etc.
- new trends in linguistics are interconnected, interconditioned that imply extralinguistic factors of the language on the whole.

The literary review of linguistic personality from pragmatic point of view makes it inevitable to introduce the new term – "discourse". Discourse (from French "discourse"- "speech") is a coherent text with extralinguistic, pragmatic, sociocultural, psychological and other factors; it is a text used in conceptual aspect. It is the speech, which is considered as purposeful social activity, and as the component participating in interaction of people and mechanisms of their consciousness (cognitive processes). The notions of "text" and "discourse" are correlative, but not equivalent. Text is a part of discourse; it is created in the

process of discourse. Despite the differences between the notions of text and discourse, they cannot be completely separated since they are closely correlated with one another in terms of their users (addresser and addressee, i.e. author and reader), relationship (text is a part or result of discourse) etc. Although different linguists define discourse in various ways, they all back up the claim that discourse is interpreted in the context and based on specific situation. It is the belief of majority prominent linguists that in the process of discourse analysis, particularly in literary review, linguistic, social, pragmatic, cultural, psychological factors of communication should be taken into consideration.

Stylistic means of expressing LP in literary discourse are characterized by a great number of stylistic means of emotional-evaluative, imagery and expressional character. The stylistically marked literary discourse assumes certain organization of semantic-stylistic means, which enables «foregrounding», and achievement of its efficiency. The study of linguopragmatic features of LP is aimed at revealing social and professional/occupational status, role and personal relations between communicants, gender, age, local, national and racial characteristics, emotional condition of communicants, traits of character and cultural property of the personality. The research of cognitive aspect of LP is targeted at the intellectual sphere of personality, at the process of human perception, which includes the knowledge about the world embodied in the thesaurus of LP. Each of the aforementioned levels is characterized by a certain set of linguistic means to analysis of which the following chapters of the dissertation work are devoted. Based on interdisciplinary character of LP in discourse, we can assume that semantic-stylistic, linguocognitive and linguopragmatic aspects are to be investigated linear, as their interpretation is integral whole part of anthropocentric paradigm. One of the significant issues relevant to linguopragmatic interpretation of LP in literary discourse is the notion of pragmatic intention. The study of LP in linguopragmatic approach puts forward the problem of pragmatic intention as one of the crucial means in the analyzing effectiveness of impact and perception of communication in the literary discourse. Pragmatic intention is defined as “verbalized in the text the addresser’s deliberate intention to exert influence on the addressee with the aim to cause some reconstruction in his/her world picture”. Several types of PI (pragmatic intention) can be distinguished and the impact of each can vary in certain context. Consequently, the language means, structural and semantic features in the literary discourse are selected based on the type and impact of PI.

Thus, these language units help to determine pragmatic intentions implicitly or explicitly in pragmatic analysis.

The pragmatic intention “to attract the reader’s attention” or so-called attention compelling intention is realized by means of structural transformations, which specifically include various occasional transformations of words, phraseological units, syntactical structures. Deviation from the standards of literary language being one of the widely encountered varieties of occasionalisms, is used as a device to realize pragmatic intention “to attract the reader’s attention” in literary discourse. Moreover, occasional transformations in word formation such as decomposition, rearrangement of the components, blending, clipping, the use of morphemes in isolation, violations in the morphemic word structure are extensively used to express this type of PI. All the abovementioned transformations make the language units look unusual and nonstandard thereby attracting the reader’s attention. Sometimes occasionalisms occur as key words in literary discourse and are expressed by correlated derivative units. Moreover, multiple times used key words and created occasionalisms based on the keywords not only attracts the reader’s attention, but determines the whole concept, main theme of the literary discourse.

One of the specific peculiarities of literary discourse is the factor of emotiveness and its emotional impact on the reader. Therefore, authors tend to use the pragmatic intention “to exert an emotional impact on the reader”, which is, in its turn, closely connected and combined with the other types of pragmatic intention such as the pragmatic intention to interest the reader and the one to attract the addressee’s attention. The pragmatic intention of emotional impact is mostly verbalized by the use of stylistic devices, particularly by convergence of stylistic devices, which is defined as “an accumulation of stylistic devices and expressive means within one fragment of the text. Stylistic means brought together enforce both logical and emotive emphasis of each other, thus attracting attention to certain parts of the text”.

Conclusion. To sum all above mentioned assumptions, we have proved that conducted research confirms the suggested hypothesis that the peculiarity of LP in literary discourse is revealed in a specific linguistic form of reflection of its semantic-stylistic, pragmatic, cognitive, national and cultural characteristics that represent a certain correlate of features of spiritual aspect of LP. In the conceptual basis and proposed methodology of article the study of LP in linguopragmatic approach effectively employs pragmatic intentions as a means

of representing individual picture of LP by attracting attention, interesting the reader, exerting emotional impact, activating knowledge structures, stimulating the addressee's creativity, representing the conceptual world picture.

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